

PREDICT-6G to the Test: An Industry 4.0 Use Case for Deterministic 6G Networks via AI-Enabled Multi-Domain Orchestration

David Rico-Menendez⁽¹⁾, Antonio de la Oliva⁽¹⁾
drico@pa.uc3m.es, aoliva@it.uc3m.es

⁽¹⁾Dpto. de Telemática, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Avenida Universidad 30, Leganes, Madrid.

Abstract—The vision for 6G is built on the need for predictability, reliability, and time-sensitiveness (i.e. deterministic networking), yet achieving deterministic communication across diverse network domains remains challenging. PREDICT-6G addresses this gap by pioneering an AI-driven, multi-domain framework that integrates deterministic networking principles across heterogeneous infrastructures. By combining a Multi-Domain Data Plane (MDP) with an AI-driven Multi-Stakeholder Inter-Domain Control Plane (AICP), the project enables seamless orchestration of end-to-end deterministic services, ensuring stringent latency, reliability, and synchronization across 3GPP (B5G), TSN, DetNet, and Wi-Fi technologies.

This paper reviews the key highlights of PREDICT-6G and introduces the results obtained.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation & Background

The evolution of 6G networks is expected to unlock a new era of deterministic, ultra-reliable, and time-sensitive communications, enabling a wide range of critical applications in *industrial automation, connected mobility, digital twins, and sensing-driven services*. However, delivering predictable, reliable, and time-sensitive networking across heterogeneous network domains remains a fundamental challenge. Current deterministic networking solutions—such as *IEEE Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) and IETF Deterministic Networking (DetNet)*—are limited to isolated domains and lack a unified approach to achieving multi-domain, cross-technology determinism [1].

PREDICT-6G addresses this gap by designing a comprehensive end-to-end (E2E) deterministic network framework, seamlessly integrating *cellular, TSN, DetNet, and Wi-Fi* into a unified architecture. The project envisions a multi-technology, multi-domain deterministic network infrastructure capable of dynamically adapting to service demands while ensuring strict latency, reliability, and synchronization guarantees [2].

The project’s key research and innovation objectives include:

- Developing a scalable, AI-driven deterministic control and management framework.
- Automating the definition, provisioning, monitoring, and life-cycle management of deterministic services.
- Ensuring seamless interoperability across TSN, DetNet, 3GPP (5G/6G), and Wi-Fi technologies
- Establishing a cross-domain orchestration model that enables deterministic networking at a large-scale, multi-stakeholder level.

This paper presents an overview of the PREDICT-6G framework through the deployment and evaluation of a multi-domain Industry 4.0 demonstration. Our work highlights how the unified roles of the Multi-domain Data Plane (MDP) and the AI-driven Inter-domain Control-Plane (AICP) deliver deterministic networking across heterogeneous domains, with experimental results validating the framework’s stringent latency, reliability, and synchronization guarantees.

II. PREDICT-6G ARCHITECTURE

The PREDICT-6G framework is built upon a modular architecture that enables predictable, reliable, and deterministic communication across diverse network domains. At its core, the architecture is organized into three principal components that work together to abstract the complexity of heterogeneous networks and ensure end-to-end deterministic service delivery. These components are:

- 1) A technology-agnostic Multi-Domain Data Plane (MDP) that implements deterministic networking based on IETF DetNet principles.
- 2) An AI-driven Multi-Stakeholder Inter-Domain Control Plane (AICP) that leverages adaptive intelligence to orchestrate and optimize network configurations.

In the following subsections, we detail each component of the PREDICT-6G architecture.

A. AI-driven Multi-Stakeholder Inter-Domain Control Plane (AICP) and Cross-Domain Orchestration

The AICP introduces adaptive intelligence into deterministic networking by leveraging *Digital Twins, AI/ML algorithms, and real-time telemetry* to orchestrate and optimize network configurations across domains. In addition to its core functions, the AICP plays a crucial role in achieving end-to-end synchronization and service assurance across diverse infrastructures.

At its foundation, the AICP models and simulates network conditions at both the end-to-end and domain levels through its integrated Digital Twin framework, enabling real-time performance forecasting, proactive anomaly detection, and intelligent resource allocation. AI/ML models then analyze historical and real-time traffic patterns to optimize path computation, scheduling policies, and cross-domain network configurations, thereby ensuring deterministic behavior across all domains. [3]

Figure 1. High-level control architecture and abstraction modeling.

A key aspect of this control plane is its role in enabling cross-domain orchestration. As shown in Figure 1, by providing a unified, interoperable control layer supported by open, programmable interfaces (PREDICT-6G Open APIs), AICP facilitates deterministic service provisioning across multiple operators and administrative domains. These open APIs offer a standardized way for different network domains to exchange configuration and status information, thereby unifying the deterministic transport of packet flows, leveraging cross-domain traffic engineering, per-flow SLA enforcement, and deterministic routing policies, with dynamic network reconfiguration in an E2E fashion. Moreover, the framework is designed to be forward-compatible with emerging 6G technologies, ensuring that the principles of deterministic networking remain integral to the next-generation wireless ecosystem.

In summary, the AICP not only manages intelligent resource orchestration and optimization via Digital Twins and AI/ML but also provides the necessary inter-domain orchestration through its open APIs, effectively bridging heterogeneous networks. This combined capability establishes the foundation for a next-generation deterministic 6G ecosystem, which combines network predictability, reliability, and AI-driven automation. [4]

B. Multi-Domain Data Plane (MDP)

The Multi-Domain Data Plane (MDP) is built on DetNet principles to provide a unified, deterministic data transport layer across multiple network domains. The DetNet data plane is structured into two sub-layers: the forwarding sub-layer and the service sub-layer. The forwarding sub-layer carries the information needed to reach the next hop and delivers essential QoS functions (e.g., via queuing mechanisms) by leveraging the underlying Layer-2 connectivity. Meanwhile, the service sub-layer implements advanced functionalities, notably the Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Function (PREOF), which is enabled by encoding specific flow attributes—such as flow identity and sequence number—in packets.

To fully support these functionalities, we adopt an MPLS over UDP/IP approach, as shown in Figure 2. This choice allows us to implement both the forwarding and service sub-

layer features of the DetNet data plane. Leveraging DetNet, the MDP integrates multiple domains by configuring boundary nodes as Detnet routers with additional functions. These routers perform three primary roles: forwarding (transmitting packet flows between domains), encapsulation, and decapsulation. The end-to-end path is computed globally by considering the service requirements and the capabilities of each domain at the AICP. The service sub-layer can employ PREOF to meet reliability requirements that individual domains cannot satisfy on their own by using a domain-specific frame replication mechanism, thus enhancing determinism by replicating packets, eliminating duplicates, and ordering them to minimize jitter. [5]

DetNet routers enable seamless cross-domain integration by translating the encapsulation markers that are unique to each network segment. They read the S-Label used to identify flows and then re-encode it into the marker format of the adjacent domain. This abstraction of internal TSN mechanisms ensures that the deterministic properties of the traffic are preserved as it moves across different network segments.

III. RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this use case, we demonstrate multi-domain deterministic communications through the remote control of a robot dog via a Digital Twin (DT). The DT provides a real-time virtual representation of the robot, enabling precise monitoring and control over its actions. Commands generated from the DT traverse multiple network domains before reaching the robot: they are first transmitted over an experimental TSN-enabled Wi-Fi network, then forwarded through an IEEE 802.1 TSN ethernet infrastructure, and finally delivered via a TSC 5G network link to the robot. This end-to-end path is illustrated in Figure 3.

The control loop is designed to mimic critical TSN characteristics. Specifically, the control application sends a 0.1 KB command packet every 10 ms to instruct the robot, while the robot sends a 0.1 KB odometry feedback packet every 20 ms to update its virtual representation. Although these packet sizes are slightly larger than those typically seen in conventional TSN traffic, they are well-suited to the requirements of this demonstration.

Figure 2. MDP architecture ensuring deterministic networking across domains.

Figure 3. Multi-domain Industry 4.0 scenario: Demonstration of real-life deployment of PREDICT-6G on a multi-domain scenario with TSN over Wi-Fi, Ethernet, and 5G.

From the PREDICT-6G perspective, the scenario requires allocating, providing and strictly guaranteeing two TSN services across three different technological domains. This ensures that the deterministic flow of control and feedback packets remains unaffected by other traffic in the network, thereby proving the effectiveness of our framework in maintaining end-to-end determinism in a multi-domain environment.

A. Deployment of the Multi-Domain Deterministic Data Plane

As stated in the previous section, the deployment of the Multi-Domain Data Plane (MDP) involves an infrastructure composed of three distinct network domains, each capable of Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) in its own way. The MDP is designed to understand, coordinate, and enable the TSN functionalities of each domain, ensuring end-to-end deterministic service delivery and synchronization.

In our implementation, the three domains are integrated as follows:

Wi-Fi TSN Domain: This domain extends TSN principles to wireless environments. It incorporates IEEE 802.1Qbv-based time-aware scheduling and over-the-air IEEE 802.1AS synchronization. Additionally, UDP ports are used to differentiate TSN traffic from non-TSN traffic, enabling proper classification and handling of critical flows. [6]

Ethernet TSN Domain: This domain leverages IEEE 802.1Qbv for time-aware shaping and IEEE 802.1AS for precision time synchronization, along with Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability (FRER) as defined in IEEE 802.1CB. VLAN headers are utilized to classify traffic, and these tags are subsequently mapped into VXLAN identifiers to support consistent traffic classification across domains.

3GPP Domain: This TSN-enabled 5G network domain employs Device-Side TSN Translators (DS-TT) and Network-

Side TSN Translators (NW-TT), in combination with network slicing, to prioritize TSN traffic and guarantee deterministic performance. These functions abstract the internal 3GPP-specific procedures, allowing the domain to participate seamlessly in end-to-end deterministic service provisioning. [7]

These three network domains are interconnected via PREDICT-6G DetNet-based MDP that acts as an intermediate coordination layer. In our implementation, the end-to-end paths are configured by the AICP E2E Path Computation entity. Figure 2 provides a step-by-step illustration of the header encapsulation and tunneling process, showing how DetNet preserves and enables the TSN capabilities of each domain across the entire network.

B. AI-Controlled Control Plane Integration

In our deployment, the AICP is composed of both *local management domains* and an *E2E management domain*, as depicted in Figure 1:

Local Management Domain: Each domain (e.g., Wi-Fi TSN, wired TSN, or 3GPP TSN) includes its own set of control and monitoring components (*Monitoring, Exposure, Automation, Path Computation Element (PCE), and Digital Twin (DT)*) that interact with domain-specific configuration agents. This ensures that domain-level QoS requirements are met through local resource allocation, scheduling, and synchronization mechanisms.

E2E Management Domain: At the top level, a centralized E2E controller (the AICP) orchestrates the deterministic paths across domains. It coordinates local controllers, retrieves global topology information, and computes multi-domain paths holistically. Additionally, it leverages real-time telemetry and digital twin modeling to predict traffic behavior, proactively detect anomalies, and optimize end-to-end resource usage.

When a service request with specific QoS requirements arrives, the AICP coordinates a streamlined workflow across the involved domains (Figure 4). First, the Service Automation component receives the request and triggers the process. Then, the Path Computation module retrieves topology information via Topology Exposure and computes a suitable path. Subsequently, Resource Configuration allocates the necessary resources in each local domain, while Measurement Collection continuously monitors performance and feeds real-time data into the digital twin and AI/ML models. Finally, based on this feedback, the AICP dynamically adjusts configurations

to ensure the service meets its deterministic QoS objectives.

By merging local domain intelligence with a global coordination layer, the AICP delivers seamless deterministic services across heterogeneous technologies.

Figure 4. Service Commissioning at domain level

C. Performance Evaluation and Key Results

The final experiments were conducted in the 5TONIC laboratory, where detailed measurements were collected to evaluate the performance of the PREDICT-6G architecture under realistic operational conditions. The key findings can be summarized as follows:

- **End-to-End Latency:** The system consistently achieved a round-trip time (RTT) of 14–15 ms, corresponding to a one-way latency of approximately 7.5 ms in 99% of the measurements.
- **Packet Loss:** No packet losses were observed for the deterministic flows, even under high levels of background traffic injected at various points in the network.
- **Adaptive Service Allocation:** The AICP effectively managed resource allocation across the multi-domain infrastructure, ensuring compliance with deterministic constraints (e.g., latency and jitter).
- **Predictive Digital Twins:** The digital twin framework identified potential bottlenecks before they impacted performance, allowing the AICP to proactively reconfigure network parameters.

These results validate the multi-domain deterministic networking framework, demonstrating its ability to meet the stringent requirements of industrial automation and other latency-critical applications. In addition to this, the AI-driven approach proved instrumental in maintaining service reliability and in optimizing performance across different domains. To isolate the contributions of each network domain, background traffic was introduced at multiple ingress points in the network. Despite these additional loads, the time-sensitive traffic remained unaffected, maintaining its deterministic guarantees. To quantify the contributions of each network domain, table I summarizes the measured latency values along with the overall end-to-end performance:

Table I
LATENCY CONTRIBUTIONS PER DOMAIN AND OVERALL END-TO-END PERFORMANCE

Component/Domain	Latency (ms)
Wi-Fi TSN Domain	2.0–2.5
5G TSN Domain	4.0–4.5
Ethernet TSN Domain	<1
DetNet Data Plane Overhead	<1
Overall E2E (One-Way)	≈7.5
Overall E2E (RTT)	14–15

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the PREDICT-6G framework successfully demonstrates that end-to-end deterministic networking can be achieved across heterogeneous domains by integrating a Multi-Domain Data Plane with an AI-driven Inter-domain Control Plane. Our experimental evaluation confirms that the framework meets stringent latency, reliability, and synchronization requirements under realistic conditions. These results underscore the potential of our approach to support critical applications, such as industrial automation and connected mobility. Future work will focus on refining the integration and extending the solution to additional network scenarios while further validating its scalability and robustness.

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